

Promising cultures and their suitability for cropping. Orissa, India.

Culture or variety	Yield av (t/ha) for 2 years	Total duration (days)	Cropping suitability
CR126-42-1/Ratna	6.1	110-115	1st crop (Feb-Mar)
Kalinga 2	6.0	115-120	-do-
CH1039-6-106	5.3	110-115	-do-
K28-1	5.1	105-110	-do-
Cauvery/CH988-3	6.1	130-135	Main crop May to June sowing
IR24	5.8	140-145	-do-
HXG60-49	6.1	130-135	-do-
K336-1	5.5	128-130	Late planting, i.e. Aug planting
HP30	5.8	128-130	-do-
P33-C-78	5.4	125-130	-do-

medium-lift irrigation facilities an effort is made to introduce rice double-cropping. But low temperature becomes a problem at germination and during the seedling stage for the first crop sown in February—March and the duration is prolonged. There is presently no high-yielding variety that can be harvested in late June or early July. Seed dormancy

is important for varieties grown in the first crop because the harvest coincides with the heavy rains. Realizing the vast potential of the region, the Indian Council for Agricultural Research has established a research center at Manipur with headquarters at Shillong for all aspects of crop, animal, and fishery sciences. Preliminary trials with a large

number of breeding material from AICRIP, CRR1, and IRRI were conducted in 1977 and 1978. Promising varieties for early, normal, and late-planted conditions were identified (see table).

In the State, large areas under 1 to 1.5 m of water grow local deepwater rices such as Taothabi, which yields only 0.5 t/ha.

Heavy rainfall and high humidity most of the year favor weed growth; about 60% are monocots. Hand weeding is the best control method but it increases production costs. Good herbicides and varieties with ability to compete well are needed.

A hybridization program involving local and hill rices such as Moirang-phou, Khonorulu, and Ryllo-red and other high yielding varieties was initiated to develop early-maturing, high-yielding, cold-tolerant rice varieties suitable for Manipur. ■

Natural outcrossing on cytoplasmic male sterile lines of rice under tropical conditions

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Rice scientists in China have shown that heterosis can be exploited commercially in rice through a cytoplasmic-genic male sterility system. On the average, 33-45% (in one case, 74%) seed set is obtained through natural outcrossing on cytosterile lines grown in isolation with restorer lines, in hybrid seed production plots. Information on the extent of natural outcrossings on male sterile lines of rice grown in the tropics is limited.

During the 1980 dry season, we planted two cytosterile lines (Zhen Shan 97A and V20A, from China) along with their respective maintainer lines (Zhen Shan 97B and V20B) in two isolation plots with an isolation distance of 60 m. The maintainer line, used as pollen source, was planted in a 3- × 3-m plot with 20- × 20-cm spacing. Fifty plants of a cytosterile line were planted at 30- × 20-cm spacing in 5 rows on each side of

Layout plan of outcrossing experiment at IRRI.

the pollen-source plot. The first row of 10 plants was 30 cm from the pollen source; the second, 50 cm; the third, 70 cm; the fourth, 90 cm; and the fifth, 110

cm (see figure).

One of the primary panicles of each of the male sterile plants was bagged at flowering. The other panicles were kept

Seed setting on 2 cytosterile lines in relation to direction and distance from the pollen source. IRRI, 1980 dry season.

Direction	Seed set (%)					Mean (%)
	30 cm	50 cm	70 cm	90 cm	110 cm	
<i>Cytosterile Zhen Shan 97A</i>						
Southwest	28.2	24.9	19.5	17.1	22.0	22.3
Southeast	21.3	11.5	4.5	6.0	3.6	9.4
Northwest	16.8	1.3	4.1	6.9	4.1	8.0
Northeast	3.9	1.6	1.4	0.6	1.1	1.7
Mean	17.6	11.3	7.5	1.6	7.7	10.4
<i>Cytosterile V20A</i>						
Southwest	19.0	10.1	11.9	11.7	9.1	12.4
Southeast	19.9	7.3	8.0	11.2	10.0	11.3
Northwest	8.9	8.9	4.6	2.5	2.9	5.6
Northeast	8.6	3.2	1.2	0.9	1.0	3.0
Mean	14.1	7.4	6.4	6.6	5.8	8.1

open for natural outcrossing. The extent of outcrossing on the male sterile plants, located at various distances from the pollen source, was determined by comparing the seed set on two randomly selected, unbagged panicles with that on bagged panicles. The data were adjusted in relation to percentage seed set of the pollen sources (94.4% for Zhen Shan 97B and 86.3% for V20B).

The two cytosterile lines did not set any seed on the bagged panicles. This

indicated the stability of their male sterility system. Seed set on the open pollinated panicles varied with the cytosterile line, direction of planting, and distance in relation to the pollinator (see table). Some individual plants gave as high as 35-45% seed set. Cytosterile Zhen Shan 97A showed higher seed set than V20A, probably because of its slightly better panicle exertion and synchronized flowering in relation to the pollen source. The higher seed set on the

male sterile plants located in southwest and southeast directions than on the plants located in the other two directions may have been caused by the prevailing wind direction (mostly north-northeast) during the flowering period (18 Feb - 16 Mar). Seed set was higher on plants 30 cm away from the pollen source than on plants located further away. The effect of distance up to 110 cm on natural outcrossing was, however, less pronounced on the plot in the southwest, which lay across the direction of wind. Therefore, it should be possible to obtain satisfactory seed set in hybrid seed production plots by growing five rows of a cytosterile line (1-m wide strip) alternately with one row of pollen source.

Although we did not practice manual flag leaf clipping and supplemental pollination, as in China, the results are encouraging. Further increase in natural outcrossing on rice cytosterile lines should be possible through selection or breeding, or both, of male sterile lines possessing shorter flag leaves, well-exserted panicles, and spikelets with exserted stigma. ■

Genetic composition of parents used in crosses and of subsequent rice varieties

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Plant breeders develop most improved crop varieties by hybridization or crossbreeding. In 1975, IRRI began a study of Asian plant breeders' use of semidwarf rice varieties as parents in their crosses. The data were collected at 14 research centers: 7 centers in India, 2 in Korea, and 1 each in Bangladesh, Indonesia, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand.

We speculated that *cross analysis* might be used as a tool in predicting the genetic composition of future crop varieties. We compared data on rice cultivars that Asian plant breeders crossed over a 10-year period (1965-75) with data on the genetic composition of the improved rice varieties released and recommended to farmers 5 years

Comparison of use of varieties as parents in crosses and genetic composition of improved rice varieties released from 1965-80. 355 randomly selected crosses involving 819 parents at 7 research centers and 202 varieties involving 433 parents. IRRI, 1980.

later (1975-1980) in the same countries. Five or six years is about the minimum time required to advance the progeny of a cross to the varietal stage.

In 1980, a list of 202 improved rice varieties, developed locally and released in the 7 Asian countries, was compiled from records of the IRRI-sponsored